

Reducing the trap density in MAPbI₃ based perovskite solar cells via Bromide chemistry

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Abstract

The past decade has witnessed tremendous advancement in the field of halide perovskite (PSK) as a choice of material for high-performing solar cells fabrication. Here, we investigate the impact of the halide exchange through *N*-Bromosuccinimide (*NBS*) treatment in MAPbI₃ based solar cells to improve stability. We observed the partial halide exchange (I⁻ to Br⁻) or the filling of halide (X⁻) vacancy upon treatment of different *NBS* concentrations experimentally by spectroscopic and diffractograms studies. We noted halide exchange impact the crystallization and is beneficial in improving the moisture-resistivity of the perovskite layer, as well as enhancing the photovoltaic performance. The optimized 0.5% *NBS*/PSK treated PSC exhibited a power conversion efficiency of 17.87% due to an increment in open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) and short circuit current (J_{sc}). We noted improved film quality upon Br substitution, eventually, it helps to lower the trap density, reducing non-radiative recombination and renders the enhancement of long-term stability of PSC.

Introduction

A sustainable source of energy is critical for our planet, as the ones contributing to the climate warming process are supposed to be impractical in the long term. This has fueled energy-related research and finding scalable, cost-effective, and revolutionary photovoltaic (PV) materials is of immediate interest. The requirement to develop innovative materials and their nanoscale architecture to translate into a practical application can drastically reduce the cost. Compared to silicon counterpart^[1], the easy synthetic approach makes perovskite absorber potentially attractive material for solar cells, to power our planet.^[2] The competitive power conversion efficiency (PCE) reported (>25%) makes it revolutionary rather than evolutionary technology, which can be further improved by minimizing the interfacial losses.^[3] Reports suggest, that the electron-hole pair can travel far and wider than exciting thin-film-based solar cells, and efforts have been laid to discover new architects to push the light-harvesting properties.^[4-7] Sincere efforts have been laid to boost the PCE, however, quantifying the materials which are less sensitive to moisture is foremost. Halide perovskites display attractive properties for their use in thin-film based PV, such as a high absorption coefficient, high charge carrier mobilities, and long diffusion lengths,^[5, 7, 8] which led to a remarkable increase in their PCE through the use of innovative charge selective (electron and hole transport) layers (ETLs, HTLs), interface engineering, energy level engineering.^[2, 9-11] The recombination in PSCs was investigated typically in pristine perovskite, however, reports dealing with device kinetics on passivated PSCs are scarce.

A plethora of reports on PSCs deals with the use of methylammonium lead halide perovskite, an ambipolar material that generates electron and hole pairs.^[12] Methylammonium lead iodide (MAPbI₃) perovskite display incredible performance due to its suitable optical and electronic properties. However, rapid degradation of MAPbI₃ in ambient air and moisture has resulted in poor long-term stability. To surmount the stability issue, several approaches have been adopted, including device encapsulation

with the hydrophobic organic moieties, inorganic oxides, or engineering the charge selective layers to be moisture resistant. Controllable substitution of iodide anion in MAPbI₃ with bromide (Br⁻) ions put forward an effective route to improve the moisture resistance and thus, stability of the PSCs. The improved stability is attributed to the smaller size of Br⁻ ions to I⁻ ions that transform the tetragonal phase of MAPbI₃ to the cubic phase.^[13] The substitution of the MAPbI₃ by minimal amount of Br also enables tunability of optical band gaps with a minimal impact on the light absorption of the MAPbI₃ perovskite that can be reduced with the amount of Br incorporation. Bromide-based perovskites exhibit a wider bandgap of 2.3 eV, which yields higher open-circuit voltage as compared to the iodide counterpart.^[14] Such properties make them applicable to tandem solar cell applications. The report suggests that bromide ions promote the separation of electrons and holes at grain boundaries.^[15] Br⁻ anions had a strong passivation effect on Pb interstitial and halide vacancies by forming robust ionic bonds with Pb²⁺ and hydrogen bonds (N-H...Br) with MA⁺/FA⁺ cations.^[16] Surface passivation is another effective protocol to reduce defects present at the surface of perovskites and suppress undesirable ion movement.^[17-19]

Scheme 1: (a) Reaction of *NBS* with isopropyl alcohol generating HBr, and (b) reaction of MAPbI₃ with HBr inducing partial halide exchange.

The defects present on the perovskite surface accelerate the decomposition pathways and promote nonradiative recombination that limits performance and reliability.^[20] Surface defects can be interstitial, created through vacancy, or stem from grain boundaries, and impacts carrier concentration, transport, and its recombination.^[21]

Several pre-treatment of the perovskite solution with halide precursors is being discussed in the literature for the successful solution-phase halide exchange reaction using suitable additives or acids.^[22, 23] Several methods of addition of acids (HX; X=halides) to the formation of an intermediate phase that allows the formation of well-defined pre-crystallized domains before annealing have been reported.^[24] The use of the hydrogen halides (HBr) acts as a strong donor that interacts strongly with Pb^{2+} and as a result forms bromide-plumbate complexes that are beneficial for the growth of high-quality films. The oxidation of HBr generates Br_2 that is converted to bromide ions; which gets coordinated to the Pb^{2+} centers and then partially substitute the iodide-based perovskite (MAPbI_3) to form $\text{MAPb}(\text{I}_{1-x}\text{Br}_x)_3$.^[13, 24] However, despite Br substitution observed by the doping effect of HBr, occasionally the existence of a substantial amount of H_2O in the aqueous HBr acid reduces the crystallinity of the perovskite film.^[25] To overcome such challenges, we put forward an alternative approach of employing anhydrous *N*-bromosuccinimide (*NBS*) that oxidizes secondary alcohol (isopropanol) generating HBr that could further assist in crystallinity by bromide substitution in MAPbI_3 .

The mixed halide perovskite has gained a considerable amount of attention on account of its optoelectronic behavior and enhanced stability.^[26] Bromide inclusion in the perovskite not only enhances the stability but also the carrier mobility, as well as reduces carrier recombination rates. The higher stability of the Pb-Br bonding as compared to the Pb-I resulted in improved device reliability. Owing to the presence of optimal bromide content in the perovskite precursor, enhanced “shelf-life” of the devices via bromide doping in the perovskite solution in both light and dark conditions at ambient air was reported.^[27] The role of *NBS* as a bromide precursor in $(\text{MAPbBr}_3)_{0.15}(\text{FAPbI}_3)_{0.85}$ was found to be beneficial in terms of reducing the surface defects and improving stability.^[28] We demonstrated an effective strategy to construct polycrystalline perovskite thin films with low surface roughness, and increment in grain size. Earlier, we studied the role of *NBS* in a mixed halide perovskite environment that was found to be advantageous for the perovskite’s optoelectronic properties. To unravel the *NBS* role and distinguish the influence of bromide substitution^[29], we have undertaken the task of investigating *NBS* treatment on methylammonium lead iodide (MAPbI_3) (Scheme 1). The influence of bromide treatment from *NBS* was systematically

investigated and was probed through an array of techniques, based on optical absorption spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction analysis, and microscopy. Surface studies envisage bromide incorporation in the MAPbI_3 , and the fabricated PSCs with 0.5% *NBS*/PSK treatment gave an improved performance than of pristine MAPbI_3 based PSCs. Our methodology simultaneously provides an approach to overcome defects at the interfaces, while having the beneficial effect of bromide substitution without having halide phase segregation.

Results and Discussion

To determine the effect of *NBS* treatment on the light absorption properties of the pristine MAPbI_3 and *NBS* treated PSK films after annealing (100°C), we performed the UV-vis absorption measurement. The varying concentration of *NBS* incorporated (0.3 – 4%) perovskites were studied for their optoelectronic properties. The absorption spectra for the pristine MAPbI_3 and *NBS* treated perovskite are represented (Figure 1a, Fig.S2a) and we noted a blue shift in the band edge of the perovskite film upon *NBS* treatment. It was observed that higher bromide content upon *NBS* treatment resulted in a higher bandgap, owing to the blue shift of the band edge upon the I/Br exchange. The absorption peak at concentrations >1% *NBS* treatment (1.5–4%), significantly blue shifts to a lower wavelength (Figure S2a) suggesting Br contribution as the partial replacement of I⁻ in MAPbI_3 and tuning of the optical properties. Compared to the pristine perovskite, the blue shifting of the band edge of the *NBS* treated MAPbI_3 (inset, Figure 1a), signalling the incorporation of Br after annealing and Br entered the MAPbI_3 lattice by replacing I⁻ site or filling a vacancy under temperature treatment. The bandgap (E_g) was calculated from the Tauc’s plot (Figure S1, S2b) and a gradual increase of band gap value was observed from 1.56 eV (MAPbI_3) to 1.79 eV (4% *NBS* treatment).^[23] The corresponding E_g of MAPbI_3 and different concentrations of *NBS*/PSK films are presented (Table S1). This absorption behaviour is consistent with the higher excitonic binding energy reported for bromide-based perovskites.^[30, 31]

Further, we performed photoluminescence (PL) studies to glean charge transfer behaviour at the interface with *NBS* treatment (Figure 1b). Similar to optical absorption, the addition of *NBS* also influenced the emission of the perovskite layer and notably, the band gap tuning was also reflected in the PL spectra that showed a progressive shift (blue) towards the higher energy from the 778 nm (pristine perovskite) to 722 nm for the 1% *NBS* treated perovskite (Figure S3). The systematic shift observed in the PL spectra towards the shorter wavelength suggests tuning of the energy bandgap (E_g) from lower to higher bandgap perovskite.

Figure 1. Optical and structural measurements of the pristine MAPbI₃ and NBS treated MAPbI₃ / perovskite (PSK) films at varying concentration, (a) UV-Visible absorption of pristine, (b) Tauc plot of the pristine PSK and NBS/PSK at different concentrations (c) photoluminescence spectra, (d) normalized photoluminescence spectra, (e) X-ray diffraction patterns, and (f) magnified area of the diffractograms in the 2θ range (28°-30°).

The emission from the NBS treated perovskite showed a significantly weaker PL intensity than the iodide-rich pristine perovskite, pointing that besides, defect suppression at the perovskite surface, NBS might facilitates hole extraction from perovskite.^[32-35] It is well-known that perovskites with higher bromide concentrations are known to undergo phase segregation. However, in our case, we employed an optimal range of NBS concentration of 0.3–1% for fabricating PSCs, that replaces a small proportion of iodide with bromide ions without showing the halide segregation as noted from the PL spectra. Usually, the PL emission from a halide segregated region typically displays a strong bathochromic shift (red-shift) and increased intensity, which was not observed in our case. On contrary, a hypsochromic shift (blue shift) of PL emission with lower intensity upon NBS treatment was noted. We speculate that the optimized concentration of NBS does not show any halide concentrated phase segregation.

The X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of the pristine perovskite and NBS (0.3%, 0.5%, and 1%) treated perovskite typically display similar diffraction peaks. However, the expanded area of each peak showed varied 2θ values. The diffraction peak at 14.38°, 20.28°, 28.72°, and 32.26° can be indexed to (110), (112), (200), and (211) crystal planes of the pure tetragonal phase of MAPbI₃. The peak at 12.8° is associated with the (100) crystal plane of PbI₂. In pure MAPbI₃, the dominant diffraction peak (110) appears at 14.38°; however, in case of 1% NBS treatment, Br progressively replaced I in pristine perovskite and the diffraction peak shifted to 14.72° (diffraction peak; 14.41° for 0.3% NBS, 14.61° for 0.5% NBS treated PSK films). We ascribed this peak shifting towards a higher 2θ value to the decrease in lattice spacing upon replacement of larger I⁻ (ionic radius 2.2Å) with smaller Br⁻ (ionic radius 1.96 Å). Further, Figure 1c exhibits the diffraction patterns monitored in the 2θ range of 28.5–30° for NBS/PSK varied concentration. This peak at 28.72° corresponds to the (200) plane, shifting monotonically (represented by an

arrow, Figure 1d) to a higher 2θ region, suggesting the existence of mixed halide (iodine-bromine) phase in the 3D domain. A prominent peak of PbI_2 was observed for 1% *NBS*/PSK, signifying the *NBS* treatment induces the coordination of under-coordinated Pb^{2+} during the exchange of halides (I, Br). From the diffraction pattern of 1% *NBS*/PSK film, two phases can be deduced; a newly formed $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_{3-x}\text{Br}_x$ for *NBS* concentration of 0.3%, 0.5% and 1%) phase and a PbI_2 phase.

Figure 2: XPS spectra, (a) Pb 4*f* peak of MAPbI_3 , (b) I 3*d* peak of 0.5% *NBS*/PSK, (c) Br 3*d* peak of MAPbI_3 , and (d) Br 3*d* peak of 0.5% *NBS*/PSK.

To quantify the chemical composition on the perovskite layer upon *NBS* treatment, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) measurements were conducted for pristine PSK and 0.5% *NBS*/PSK. In the Pb 4*f* spectra of MAPbI_3 , two characteristic peaks at 136.67 eV and 141.55 eV were observed and can be associated with the Pb^{2+} (Pb 4*f*_{5/2} and Pb 4*f*_{7/2}). Upon treatment of 0.5% *NBS* (Figure 2a), it exhibited a shift of around 2 eV, which demonstrates that *NBS* is chemically anchored on the surface of the MAPbI_3 crystal. The decrease in iodine peaks (I 3*d*) ratio and shift in binding energy (Figure 2b) is ascribed to the partial replacement of iodine with bromide ions in the pristine MAPbI_3 . Nevertheless, we can simultaneously detect the presence of Br from Br 3*d* peaks at 68.3 eV and 69.8 eV for 0.5% *NBS* treated *in situ* films, which were not apparent in MAPbI_3 . The C1*s* spectra of the MAPbI_3 and with 0.5% *NBS* treatment remain unaltered. (Figure S4).

The microstructure of the MAPbI_3 and 0.5% *NBS*/PSK were recorded with the help of a scanning electron microscope (SEM), the microstructure of 0.5% *NBS*/PSK exhibits complete coverage with large grains without pinholes and lesser grain boundaries (Figure 3a, b). We noted that with an increase in the concentration of *NBS* the grain size increased progressively (Figure S5). This could be aided by the fact that as soon as Br⁻ is incorporated in the perovskite crystal, the initial heterogeneous nucleation rate was induced and slowed down the crystal growth of the newly formed mixed halide perovskite.^[36] We studied the role of *NBS* for surface properties and stabilization on bromide addition by the

goniometry measurements (Figure 3c,d). The contact angle value for MAPbI_3 was 69° and this value increases to 80° upon treatment of 0.5% *NBS* (Figure 3a,b) and for other *NBS* concentrations (Figure S6).

Figure 3: Surface SEM images (a) MAPbI_3 , (b) 0.5% *NBS*/PSK; contact angle measurements of (c) MAPbI_3 , (d) 0.5% *NBS*/PSK, and (e) cross-sectional SEM-image of the 0.5% *NBS*/PSK treated PSC.

To appraise the role of *NBS* as the bromide contributor, we fabricated PSCs, in the mesoscopic *n-i-p* configuration with the structure of FTO/bl-Meso-TiO₂/ MAPbI_3 /*NBS*/Spiro-OMeTAD/Au. The cross-sectional SEM image of the devices fabricated using 0.5% *NBS*/PSK (Figure 3e), illustrates the thickness of the blocking and mesoporous TiO₂ to 131 nm, the pristine perovskite 409 nm, while the hole transport layer (Spiro-OMeTAD) was 116 nm. The current density-voltage (*J-V*) curves for the PSCs with *NBS* under the AM 1.5G illumination (100 mWcm⁻²) are shown (Figure 4a), and the corresponding PV parameters, the short-circuit current (*J*_{sc}), open-circuit voltage (*V*_{oc}), fill factor (*FF*), and PCE are listed in Table 1. The PSCs fabricated with pristine MAPbI_3 exhibited a PCE of 16.54%. (*J*_{sc}= 21.41 mAcm⁻², *V*_{oc}= 1035 mV, *FF* = 74.56%), while under similar condition, the 0.5%*NBS*/PSK (optimised concentration) based PSCs yielded a PCE of 17.87% (*J*_{sc}= 22.72 mAcm⁻², *V*_{oc} = 1074 mV, *FF* = 73.17 %). The addition of *NBS* as a bromide precursor on the perovskite layer influenced the energy gap and thus the PV parameters *V*_{oc}, *J*_{sc}, and finally PCE. The performance enhancement is due to the improvement in charge separation and carrier diffusion, arising from lower charge recombination. The voltage deficit was minimized by 34 mV. The incident photon-to-current conversion efficiency (Figure 4b) measurement demonstrates a broad absorption range, with an absorption onset at around 780 – 790 nm. The current-density curves for 0.3% and 1% *NBS*/PSK based PSCs are depicted in Figure S7 and Table S2.

Figure 4: (a) J - V graph of pristine and 0.5% NBS/PSK treated PSCs, (b) corresponding incident-photon-to-current-efficiency graphs, (c) steady-state output for 600 s at 850 mV, (d) maximum power point tracking for the 0.5% NBS/PSK treated PSC at 850 mV without encapsulation for 50h under nearly 1 sun illumination at ambient condition. The statistical PV parameters of (e) V_{oc} (f) PCE of the pristine and 0.5% NBS treated PSCs.

The stabilized power output at maximum power point for 600 seconds is tracked for the $MAPbI_3$, as well as 0.5% NBS/PSK treated PSCs were measured (Figure 4c) with no apparent changes. Furthermore, the long-term operational stability of the $MAPbI_3$ and optimized concentration of 0.5% NBS/PSK unencapsulated PSC were examined at the maximum power point voltage under continuous light illumination at nearly 1 sun for ~50 hours at ambient atmospheric conditions (25–27°C, ~60% RH environment).

Table 1: PV parameters:

DEVICE	V_{oc} (MV)	J_{sc} (MA/CM ²)	FF (%)	PCE (%)	R_s (Ω)	R_{SHUNT} (K Ω)
$MAPbI_3$	1035	21.41	74.56	16.54	56.65	27.67
Average	1020 (± 15)	21.41 (± 0.38)	71.87 (± 4.13)	15.76 (± 0.77)		
0.5% NBS/PSK	1074	22.72	73.17	17.87	53.11	40.37
Average	1066 (± 14)	22.33 (± 0.63)	70.80 (± 2.37)	16.92 (± 0.95)		

Notably, the NBS treated PSCs maintained almost 70% of their initial performance as compared to $MAPbI_3$ ^[20] based PSC in our previous report, which retained only 29% of its initial device performance. (Figure 4d).^[20, 37] The statistics of PV performance (V_{oc} and PCE; J_{sc} and FF) are also presented (Figure 4 e-f and S8).

To access the impact of NBS treatment on the density of defects grown in the perovskite layer, the hole only devices with the structure FTO/PEDOT:PSS/ $MAPbI_3$ / NBS /Au are fabricated.^[38, 39] The I - V curves of the devices with and without NBS treatment are represented (Figure 5 a,b). The trap-state density is determined by the trap-filled limit voltage (V_{TFL}) following the equation:

$$N_{defects} = \frac{2\epsilon_r\epsilon_0V_{TFL}}{eL^2} \quad (1)$$

Where L represents the thickness of the perovskite ϵ_r and ϵ_0 are the relative dielectric constant of $MAPbI_3$ and vacuum permittivity respectively, and e is the elementary charge. The trap-filled limit voltage (V_{TFL}) was found to be 0.37 V for $MAPbI_3$ and 0.12 V for 0.5% NBS treated PSC. The calculated defect densities ($N_{defects}$) are $8.05 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and $2.61 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ for $MAPbI_3$ and 0.5% NBS/PSK treated PSCs. The lower defect density in the NBS treated device can be attributed to the improved crystallinity and favorable orientation of the perovskite grains upon NBS treatment. The charge transport and the recombination of PSCs are mainly influenced by the resistance of the device. To understand the influence of NBS treatment on the charge dynamics of PSCs we performed the electrical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurements under dark conditions at an applied voltage of 850 mV and the fitted graphs are depicted (Figure S9). The equivalent circuit model of R_s+R_{rec}/CPE (Figure S10) includes the series resistance (R_s), and the recombination resistance (R_{recom}), while the constant phase element defining the carrier diffusion is represented as CPE.^[40] The Nyquist plots (Figure 5c) reveal the higher R_{recom} based on 0.5% NBS treatment suggesting suppressed charge recombination at the perovskite/HTL interface, resulting in an enhanced V_{oc} and J_{sc} . The value for R_{recom} for the $MAPbI_3$ and the 0.5% NBS treated PSCs was calculated to be 213.6 Ω and 752.3 Ω respectively, exemplifies an improved charge transfer behavior, with a lower surface defect for the NBS treated PSC.

Conclusion

We demonstrated the halide exchange (I to Br) in pure methylammonium lead iodide perovskite via NBS treatment on the perovskite layer. The NBS solution in isopropyl alcohol generates HBr that further facilitates the bromide substitution in the perovskite layer post-annealing. The blue shift in the absorbance spectra and the crystallinity enhancement with the inclusion of bromide ions were ascribed by the XRD measurements. The NBS treatment influences the crystallization kinetics, favoring compact thin film with large crystalline grains. The optimized 0.5% NBS/PSK -based PSCs lead to improved photovoltaic performances and device stability without showing any halide phase segregation. Impedance spectroscopy attributes higher charge recombination resistance, this, in turn, will reduce non-radiative recombination at the interface and improve charge transfer dynamics after optimal NBS treatment. Our study highlights the halide exchange (bromide exchanged with iodide) as an important criterion in improving the device stability by reducing the iodide vacancy in the perovskite and improving the solar cell performances.

Figure 5: Current density-voltage characteristics of the hole only devices (a) MAPbI₃ (b) with 0.5% NBS/PSK treatment. (c) Nyquist plots for the MAPbI₃ and 0.5% NBS treated PSCs measured with an applied voltage of 850 mV and under dark condition.

Experimental Section

Materials:

N-Bromo succinimide (NBS) (anhydrous, 99% purity) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Lead Iodide (PbI₂, 99.99%) was purchased from TCI, Methylammonium Iodide (MAI) was purchased from Great Cell Solar. Spiro-OMeTAD was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Anhydrous dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), anhydrous chlorobenzene (CBZ), anhydrous isopropanol was purchased from Acros Organics. 4-tertbutylpyridine (*t*-BP), lithium bistrifluoromethylsulfoni- imide (Li-TFSI), titanium diisopropoxide bis(acetylacetonate) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Titanium dioxide paste (30-NRD) was purchased from Dyesol. All the chemicals were used as received without further purification.

Device Fabrication

The fluorine-doped tin oxide (FTO) coated glasses (TEC 7) was used as electrode and were cleaned before use, firstly by ultrasonication (2% Hellmanex water solution for 30 minutes) followed by rinsing with deionized water, acetone, and isopropanol (IPA) sequentially and finally the substrates were treated under UV-Ozone for 30 minutes for the removal of further residue. TiO₂ compact layer was deposited on the cleaned FTO substrate via spray pyrolysis at 500 °C using a precursor solution of titanium diisopropoxide bis(acetylacetonate) in anhydrous ethanol (1:19). After the spraying, the substrates were left at 500 °C for 30 minutes and left to cool down to acquire room temperature. Followed by this, a 150–200 nm of mesoporous TiO₂ layer was deposited by a spin coating process, for this a (1:8) TiO₂ paste (Dyesol 30 NR-D) diluted in ethanol for 30 s at 4000 rpm was used. The substrates were dried at 125 °C and then annealed until 500 °C in a four-step temperature ramp and maintained at 500 °C for 30 min. When the room temperature is attained, the substrates were treated under UV-Ozone for 15 minutes and transferred to an argon-filled glove-box for perovskite layer deposition. The precursor solution for preparing the MAPbI₃ was prepared by dissolving MAI and PbI₂ in 1:1 ratio. The perovskite solution was spin-coated in a two-step sequence at 1000 and 4000 rpm for 10 and 30 s, respectively. During the second step, 110 μL of chlorobenzene was dripped as an antisolvent approach on the substrate 10 s before the end of the spinning process. The perovskite-coated substrates were annealed at 100 °C for 50 mins in a glovebox. On acquiring room temperature, the passivation layer (0.3%, 0.5%, and 1% NBS solution in isopropanol) was deposited and annealed at 100 °C for 8 minutes respectively. Once it is cooled down to room

temperature, the hole transport layer was deposited. Spiro-OMeTAD (70 mM) was prepared by dissolving the corresponding number of materials in 1 mL chlorobenzene. Spiro-OMeTAD was doped by adding bis-(trifluoromethylsulfoni- imide lithium salt (Li-TFSI) and 4-*tert*-Butylpyridine (*t*-BP) in the molar ratio 0.5 and 3.3 respectively. 40 μL of HTM solutions were spin-coated atop of the perovskite layer at 4000 rpm for 30 s, in an argon-filled glove box. To finish the device fabrication, a gold layer of 70 nm as cathode was thermally evaporated under a low vacuum (10⁻⁶ torr). All solutions were prepared inside an argon-filled glove box with controlled moisture and oxygen conditions (O₂ <10 ppm, H₂O < 2 ppm).

Device characterization

The fabricated solar cells figure of merit was measured using current density–voltage (*J*–*V*) curves, recorded with a Keithley 2400 source-meter under AM 1.5 G, 100 mW cm² illumination from a 450 W AAA solar simulator (ORIEL, 94023 A). NREL certified monocrystalline silicon solar cell was used for calibration. A black metal mask (0.09 cm²) was used over the square size active area (0.5 cm²) to reduce the influence of scattered light. Photovoltaic parameters including *J*_{sc}, *V*_{oc}, fill factor (FF), and power conversion efficiency (PCE) were extracted from the photocurrent–voltage (*J*–*V*) curves of the solar cells (scan rate: 100 mV s⁻¹, pre-sweep delay: 10 s). The external quantum efficiency (EQE) measurements were carried out using a 150W Xenon lamp attached to Bentham PVE300 motorized 1/4m monochromator as the light source. Mott-schottky and Electrochemical impedance measurements were done using Biologic SP-300 impedance analyzer inside a Faradaic chamber.

Thin-film Characterization

The morphology of the surface with and without the passivation layer was examined by the scanning electron microscope (SEM). The thin films were prepared on quartz substrate by spin coating of pristine MAPbI₃ and (0.3, 0.5, and 1%) NBS coated MAPbI₃ were used for structural characterization. X-ray diffractograms were recorded using the D8 Advance diffractometer from Bruker (Bragg-Brentano geometry, with an X-ray tube Cu Kα, λ=1.5406 angstrom). A scan of 5-10° was selected with an acquisition time of 1°/min. The absorption spectra were measured using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Varian Cary 50 UV/Vis Spectrophotometer). The steady-state Photoluminescence (PL) measurements were recorded with a fluorescence spectrophotometer (Perkin Elmer Instrument LS55). For PL measurement perovskite film with and without NBS were spin-coated on quartz coated substrate and

excitation wavelength was 450 nm. The samples were excited from the back (glass side). X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was carried out on a SPECS system (BERLIN, GERMANY) equipped with Phoibos 150 1D-DLD analyzer with a monochromator Al K α radiation (1486.7 eV).

Acknowledgments

This work received funding from the European Union H2020 Programme under a European Research Council Consolidator grant [MOLEMAT, 726360]. PARASOL (RTI2018-102292-B-100) and ARISE (PID2019-111774RB-100), the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation and Basque regional ELKARTEK project, ENSOL2 (KK 2020/00077).

Keywords: Bromide substitution • *N*-Bromo succinimide • hydrobromic acid • stability • lower trap state.

Supplementary Information

Detailed absorption spectra, PL spectra, XPS spectra, scanning microscopy images, contact angle, *JV* graphs, statistics, equivalent circuit impedance, Table S1, Table S2.

Declaration interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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